

Criticality Analysis of Bounding Axial Burnup Profiles for Improved Burnup Credit Implementation

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ABSTRACT

Burnup Credit (BUC) is a well-established approach in criticality-safety analyses to account for the reactivity reduction of used nuclear fuel assemblies due to their irradiation. In France, the “50-least-irradiated-cm” method has been used since the early 1980s as a conservative approach, assuming an axially uniform burnup equal to the average burnup of the 50 cm least irradiated portion of a Fuel Assembly (FA). Although approved by the French Safety Authority, this method remains penalizing. However, more advanced methods would allow for greater margins, particularly by using a non-uniform Axial Burnup Profile (ABP).

This study builds on a related paper using CASMO5/SIMULATE5 (CMS5) to generate axial burnup profiles for UOX fuel in 900 MWe reactors, from which bounding Normalized ABPs (NABP) were derived and characterized. The core simulations consider different control rod insertion depths to assess more reactive profiles. In this present paper, the reactivity of the calculated profiles is assessed through k -inf calculations, and compared with the reactivity of bounding profiles obtained from measurements performed by the La Hague reprocessing plant, and reference profiles published in the U.S. NRC’s NUREG/CR-6801 report.

For cases considering atypical control rod insertion assumptions, the burnup profiles calculated with the 3-D core code CMS5 show higher k -inf values than those from the NUREG/CR-6801 report. These results underline the importance of characterizing the irradiation history, especially the control rods insertion, when establishing bounding NABPs for BUC approach. Also, the relevance of a specific parameter for identifying the most penalizing profile is presented.

Keywords: criticality, safety, burnup, credit

1. INTRODUCTION

Burnup credit refers generally to the practice of accounting for the used fuel assembly reactivity reduction due to its irradiation in reactor, when performing criticality-safety analysis. In France, burnup credit is currently implemented through the traditional “50-least-irradiated-cm” approach that has been approved by the French safety authority since in the early 1980s and many industrial applications use this approach [1]. Although robust, this method assumes a uniform axial burnup distribution with a conservative burnup value equal to the average burnup of the 50 cm least irradiated portion of the assembly (often the upper end). However, more advanced methods would allow for greater margins, particularly by using a non-uniform Axial Burnup Profile (ABP).

Bounding Normalized ABPs (NABP) were previously determined by ORNL for US PWR FA based on a database containing 3,169 profiles calculated with 3-D core physics codes, as reported in the U.S. NRC’s NUREG/CR-6801 [2]. In France, the CEA also derived bounding NABP from the analysis of measured axial-burnup profiles (ABPs) at La Hague reprocessing plant on French 900 MWe PWRs spent FA [3]. The objective of the present work is to present updated profiles computed with modern

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3-D core codes, establish bounding axial profiles, and to compare their reactivity with both the NUREG/CR-6801 and La Hague bounding profiles.

This study extends another one [4], that examines calculated ABPs for PWR-UOX fuel in 900 MWe reactors. This study evaluated the axial burnup profiles of a representative 900 MWe French PWR UOX core, explored different Rod Cluster Control Assemblies (RCCAs) bank configuration to assess more conservative profiles, compared the resulting NABPs with NUREG/CR-6801 and La Hague bounding profiles, and proposed a parameter (the “R50” parameter) to ease the identification of the most penalizing profile.

2. METHOD

2.1. Overview

As part of efforts to determine bounding NABPs for criticality-safety assessment, this study aims to compare NABPs determined by using up-to-date nuclear data libraries and reactor core codes with previous bounding profiles from the U.S. NRC’s NUREG/CR-6801 or issued from La Hague measurements. To this end, the differences in reactivity (k_{inf}) considering all these NABPs are presented.

The comparison of NABPs is performed for three burnup ranges, consistent with the NUREG/CR-6801: average burnup of FA < 18 GWd/tU, between 18 and 30 GWd/tU, and > 30 GWd/tU. The NABPs resulting from recent calculations (presented in [4]) are determined for various RCCAs insertion depths as detailed in section 3.1.

Each NABP is composed of several axial regions and normalized to an average of 1.0. The burnup of each region is determined by multiplying the value of the normalized profile for that region to the average burnup of the FA. In this paper, the average burnup chosen are the upper bound of the relevant burnup range (i.e., 18, 30 or 45 GWd/tU). The isotopic composition of each region is determined by a 2D depletion calculation.

The modeling assumptions considered in the depletion calculations can have a significant impact on the FA reactivity. In this study, conservative assumptions are applied to have “penalizing” isotopic compositions, consistent with a criticality-safety approach. These assumptions are described in section 2.2.1 as well as their impact on reactivity (in section 2.2.3) compared to a *best-estimate* approach. Finally, for every NABPs from the related study [4], and bounding NUREG/CR-6801 and La Hague plant NABPs, k_{inf} calculations are performed to compare reactivities, using a model described in section 2.2.2.

By comparing the reactivity of different NABPs, this study aims to demonstrate through k_{inf} calculations that the strong peaking of the axial profile in the upper region of the FA—corresponding to lower irradiation near the ends of FA—has a significant impact on reactivity compared to a uniform profile based on the assembly’s average burnup. To characterize this phenomenon, a parameter “R50” is introduced. It is defined as the ratio of the average burnup of the upper 50 centimeters of the FA to the average burnup of the FA. This parameter has previously been used in criticality-safety assessment to evaluate the bounding “50-least-irradiated-cm” burnup value of any FA, this burnup value been then conservatively applied as a uniform burnup profile for criticality calculations. Moreover, the “R50” is also a relevant parameter to identify the most penalizing NABPs among others.

2.2. Calculations Schemes

2.2.1. Depletion calculation

The depletion calculations are performed to generate isotopic compositions for each axial region of FA, with each region corresponding to a specific burnup value. A depletion calculation is therefore performed for a wide range of burnup values. For intermediate burnup values not explicitly calculated, isotopic data are obtained by linear interpolation between the two nearest burnup points.

A depletion library is generated using CASMO5 in Single Assembly mode [6], simulating a 900 MWe PWR-UOX FA with 3.7 wt.% of ^{235}U enrichment (fresh fuel), water moderated and fully reflected on X and Y axis. CASMO5 is a multi-group 2D lattice deterministic code used here with the ENDF-B/VII.1 nuclear data library. An artificial geometric buckling is introduced to enforce criticality, effectively simulating leakage in an otherwise infinite system. Calculations were performed for 43 burnups distributed between 0 and 60 GWd/tU and no cooling time was considered in the simulation.

Conservative assumptions for the depletion calculation are considered on several parameters, such as the moderator and fuel temperature, the boron concentration, the insertion of control rods, or the nominal power. Penalizing values for those parameters are taken from previous studies from the French working group on Burnup Credit for PWR UOX fuel [5] and are as follows: fuel temperature of 650°C, moderator temperature of 330°C, 600 ppm of boron and a specific power of 60 W/g. As CASMO5 is a 2D code, the control rods can only be modelled fully inserted or withdrawn. The use of a fully inserted Control Rods (CR) depletion library is conservative, as it results in a lower consumption of fissile nuclides. In this study, the isotopic compositions of the upper 56 cm of the fuel assembly (FA) were determined considering CR insertion. The height of 56 cm is arbitrary, chosen from typical values in criticality-safety assessments involving a BUC approach. This method is still conservative, since CR insertion is already taken into account in the determination of the axial burnup profile (ABP) through the reduction of the burnup in the corresponding FA regions. The total impact on reactivity of the depletion calculation assumptions is presented in section 2.2.3.

The isotopic compositions of the fuel assembly profile are determined using a 2D code with conservative assumptions. This simplified approach is commonly adopted in France. Indeed, given the diversity of fuel assemblies in nuclear facilities, it is easier to perform this type of calculation rather than full core calculations.

2.2.2. K-inf calculation

Criticality calculations are performed using the MORET 6 code [7]. MORET 6 is a three-dimensional Monte Carlo neutron transport code developed by ASNR for criticality safety and reactor physics applications. It allows a detailed modeling of complex geometries and materials and performs k-effective calculations using continuous energy nuclear data libraries. The ENDF-B/VIII.0 library is used for this paper.

The k-inf calculations are performed for an infinite plan array of 900 MWe PWR-UOX FAs moderated by water modeled by a FA fully reflected on X and Y axis. A 20 cm layer of water is considered on $\pm Z$. The Zr cladding of the fuel rods and the air gap between the cladding and the fuel are modeled while structural materials such as grids and steel components are not considered.

The modeled fuel includes 12 actinides and 15 fission products, usually used in BUC approaches:

- Actinides: ^{234}U , ^{235}U , ^{236}U , ^{238}U , ^{237}Np , ^{238}Pu , ^{239}Pu , ^{240}Pu , ^{241}Pu , ^{242}Pu , ^{241}Am , ^{243}Am
- Fission products: ^{95}Mo , ^{99}Tc , ^{101}Ru , ^{103}Rh , ^{109}Ag , ^{133}Cs , ^{143}Nd , ^{145}Nd , ^{147}Sm , ^{149}Sm , ^{150}Sm , ^{151}Sm , ^{152}Sm , ^{153}Eu , ^{155}Gd .

As limited number of isotopes are considered, the fuel atomic densities are rescaled to have a total density equal to the fresh fuel.

2.2.3. Impact of depletion calculation assumptions

To evaluate the impact on reactivity of these assumptions, two sets of k-inf calculations were performed for each NABP described in chapter 3.1. Both used the same criticality model (Section 2.2.2), but with different isotopic sources:

1. The isotopic compositions from the CASMO5 depletion library with penalizing modelling assumptions (section 2.2.1), and
2. The “best-estimate” compositions obtained directly from the CASMO-SIMULATE5 (CMS5) 3D full-core simulation [4].

Within the scope of this modelling approach and fuel type, the impact of the compositions obtained with CASMO5 compared to the “best-estimate” compositions obtained with CMS5 is the following:

- ~1000 pcm for FA with an average burnup of ~18 GWd/tU
- ~3000 pcm for FA with an average burnup of ~30 GWd/tU
- ~6000 pcm for FA with an average burnup of ~45 GWd/tU

It is important to note that the irradiation history considered in the CASMO5 depletion calculation is different from those of the 3D core CMS5 calculations used to derive the NABPs.

3. NORMALIZED AXIAL-BURNUP PROFILES

3.1. Calculated NABPs

The ABP were computed using the code sequence CASMO/SIMULATE5 (CMS5). The simulated core is a representative French 900 MWe PWR loaded with UOX FA irradiated over four cycles. The cooling time between the cycles and after the unloading of the FAs was not considered. The fresh UOX fuel has an enrichment in ²³⁵U of 3.7%.

Three banks of RCCA are considered:

- Regulation bank: Ag-In-Cd (AIC) CRs, inserted into 30 cm in some FAs,
- Variable bank: Ag-In-Cd (AIC) CRs, inserted at various depths (0, 16, 48, and 95 cm),
- Hafnium rods fully inserted on FAs located at the periphery of the core, to protect the reactor vessel from the neutron fluence.

The variable bank allows us to evaluate the impact of different CR insertion and the possibility to irradiate a rodded FA during several cycles. For each insertion depth, a full simulation of the core cycles at equilibrium has been run. Therefore, four different sets of ABP (one for each insertion depth) are produced for all FAs in the core.

With 1/8 core symmetry, the CR insertions considered to determine ABP are described below in *Table I* (with FAs’ names consistent with the paper [4]):

Table I. RCCA banks insertion history of rodded FAs in 1/8e core (V: variable bank; R: regulation bank; Hf: Hafnium bank; no: no insertion of RCCA)

Rodded FAs	1-cycle burnt FA	2-cycle burnt FA			3-cycle burnt FA			4-cycle burnt FA				
	D1	D2	F2	G2	D3	F3	G3	C4	D4	E4	F4	G4
1 st cycle	V	V	no	V	V	no	V	no	V	no	no	V
2 nd cycle	-	V	R	no	V	R	no	no	V	no	R	no
3 rd cycle		-			no	no	R	no	no	no	no	R
4 th cycle		-			-			V	no	Hf	Hf	no

The ABPs are computed using 26 equally spaced axial regions. With the insertion of the variable bank during all the irradiation cycles, the calculation simulates an atypical reactor core control, which leads to NABPs that one can consider extreme and unlikely to occur. A more detailed analysis of the different NABPs used in this paper is presented in the study [4].

3.2. Measured NABPs from La Hague Plant

The CEA determined a bounding axial burnup profile based on spent FA measurements made in the late 90’s by La Hague reprocessing plant [3]. These measurements covered on 209 FA from various 900 MWe French NPPs using gamma spectrometry for ¹³⁷Cs counting with an acquisition on both sides of each FA every centimeter. The bounding NABPs were determined for two ranges of burnup: < 30

GWd/tU and ≥ 30 GWd/tU. The bounding NABPs were selected as those showing the lower normalized irradiation in the upper 60 cm of the assembly. This method stems from previous results showing that the irradiation level of the upper region of the FA drives the reactivity [1]. The resulting bounding NABPs were discretized into 11 axial regions and are detailed in the study [3]. However, this data set includes very few FAs with a burnup below 30 GWd/tU. This lack in the dataset may result in bounding NABPs that potentially do not bound all reactor core management leading to more penalizing NABPs.

3.3. NUREG/CR-6801 (ORNL) NABPs from 1997

ORNL performed 3-D core simulations on approximately 1700 FA, from 20 different US reactors operating in the mid-1990s, and determined 3169 ABPs [2]. These computations were made with the following codes: SIMULATE-3, NEMO, ANC, and PRESTO-II. The range of enrichment in ^{235}U goes from 1.24 wt.% to 4.75 wt.%. The resulting NABPs were defined over 18 equally spaced axial regions defined for three ranges of burnup: average burnup of FA < 18 GWd/tU, between 18 and 30 GWd/tU, and > 30 GWd/tU.

4. RESULTS

As a reminder, for each range of burnup, the corresponding NABPs from the 900 MWe PWR UOX fuel management simulation are multiplied to the same average burnup value (either 18, 30 or 45 GWd/tU). Their axial isotopic compositions come from depletion calculation with CASMO-5 (2D code in single assembly mode) using penalizing assumptions.

The k-inf results for each NABP and variable bank insertion depths are presented in Figure 1. Every FAs that have been rodded with the variable bank of RCCAs during their irradiation cycles are noted in red and orange. The k-inf values for the bounding NABPs, from La Hague measurements and NUREG are represented in red and blue horizontal dashed lines respectively.

Figure 1. k_{inf} for every NABP as a function of variable bank of RCCAs insertion depth – Burnup fixed to the upper bound of range.

It can be noticed that the bounding NUREG profiles lead to higher k_{inf} than the bounding La Hague profiles. As shown in [4], NUREG profiles show a lower normalized burnup value at the upper region of the FA compared to bounding profiles from La Hague, confirming that the reactivity is driven by the upper end of the FA.

Regarding the NABPs from the 3-D core simulation, inserting the variable bank of RCCAs at either 48 or 95 cm during all irradiation cycles results in some NABPs with higher k_{inf} values than the bounding NABPs from NUREG and from La Hague measurements. In particular, one FA shows a reactivity

higher by about +3500 pcm compared to the NUREG one when the variable bank is inserted at 95 cm (and +1500 pcm when inserted to 48 cm) within the second range of burnup. This FA (named “D2”) has a specific irradiation history, as it has been rodded by the variable bank of RCCAs at its first and second irradiation cycles. This result highlights the importance of knowing the irradiation history. Nevertheless, it can be noted that in some cases the reactivity increase is of the same order of magnitude as the one observed by using penalizing depletion calculation assumptions. Further studies should be conducted to assess whether the penalties applied in the 2D depletion calculations, to determine the compositions, would be sufficient to cover atypical irradiation histories.

In Figure 1, it can also be noticed that the FAs not affected by the variable RCCA bank are significantly influenced by their surrounding environment. Specifically, their NABPs shift considerably towards a more reactive profile if they are located next to a FA impacted by the variable RCCA bank, becoming even more reactive with increased insertion depth of the variable bank. This phenomenon highlights that the FA irradiation histories are strongly influenced by their nearest neighbors.

The term “end-effect” is used to describe the effect of using an ABP instead of a uniform burnup profile. The end-effect is defined as the difference in reactivity between using an ABP and using a uniform burnup profile set to the average burnup of the ABP. It indicates whether reactivity is driven by the upper part or the center part of the FA. Since all the NABPs, within their respective burnup ranges, are rescaled to the same average burnup value, their end-effects are calculated relative to the same uniform burnup profile. This approach allows us to use a single plot to evaluate both the difference in reactivity among the NABPs, and their respective conservatism relative to a uniform burnup profile. The end-effects of the various NABPs rescaled to 18, 30 or 45 GWd/tU are presented in Figure 2 along with their R50 value.

Figure 2. R50 and end-effect – Burnup fixed to the upper bound of range.

Almost all end-effects are positive, indicating that using ABP is more penalizing than a uniform burnup profile. In this application case, the end effects are positive even for low burnups due to the assumptions used in the depletion calculations (CASMO5 2D) to determine the isotopic compositions of each axial region of the assembly, in particular, the compositions of the upper 56 cm which consider CR insertion. For example, when considering a total insertion of the control rods in the depletion calculation (i.e. for the isotopic compositions of all axial regions), the end-effects are almost all negative. Therefore, it is important to calculate also the k_{inf} for a uniform profile when attempting to utilize ABPs. In this study, considering control rods insertion to generate isotopic composition only for the 56 top centimeters of the FAs increases the end-effect, making it positive.

For all burnup ranges, a linear correlation can be observed between the “R50” parameter and the variation of reactivity due to end-effect. The lower the “R50” parameter is, the more reactive the NABPs become. However, two distinct linear trends can be identified. The upper trend seems to affect only the NABPs originating from a core simulation with variable RCCA bank insertion depth of 95 cm. The splitting of the trends is mainly due to the inability of the “R50” parameter to capture the relative irradiation level of the top part of the FA below 50 cm. If the burnup of the top portion of the FA below

50 cm, compared to the overall average burnup, also has a significant impact on the reactivity of the NABP, then “R50” parameter fails to account for this effect. Consequently, other parameters can be computed to better predict the overall reactivity. One could consider using “R100” parameter (the ratio between the average burnup of the upper 100 cm of the FA and the total average burnup) but it was found to overemphasize regions closer to the center of the FA, which have less impact on reactivity. A good compromise is the “R70” parameter (the ratio between the average burnup of the upper 70 cm of the FA and the total average burnup). As shown in Figure 3, the “R70” parameter seems to properly describe the conservatism of any NABP.

Figure 3. R70 and end-effect – Burnup fixed to the upper bound of range.

The correlation between the reactivity of an NABP and its “R70” parameter appears more linear and consistent than with the “R50” parameter, at least for the first and second ranges of burnup.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to compare the reactivity of different Normalized Axial Burnup Profiles (NABP) through a criticality-safety approach. NABPs were recently determined using state-of-the-art 3-D core depletion code considering conservative reactor control conditions [4]. The reactivity of each NABP is compared with bounding NABPs from the U.S. NRC’s NUREG/CR-6801 [2] and burnup profiles measured at La Hague reprocessing plant [3]. The comparison is performed for several fixed burnup values (18, 30 and 45 GWd/tU). Isotopic compositions of each region are determined with CASMO5 modelling, considering penalizing assumptions (e.g. control rods insertion, fuel temperature, ...). These assumptions are usually considered in France when the burnup credit is applied for criticality-safety assessment.

This study shows that for some reactor operating conditions (i.e. control rods insertion depths) the NABPs generated in [4] are more reactive than the U.S. NRC’s NUREG/CR-6801 profiles and profiles derived from measures at La Hague reprocessing facility. However, some simulated irradiation history may be considered as not usual conditions (e.g. additional control rods inserted during all irradiation cycles). Nevertheless, it should be noted that a minimum level of RCCA insertion is required (under the simulated fuel management conditions considered here) to generate NABPs that can bound the measured profiles from La Hague. These results underline the importance of knowing the irradiation history. Still, in some cases, the reactivity increase associated with such reactor core controls remains of the same order of magnitude as that obtained with penalizing depletion calculation assumptions. Additional investigations are therefore needed to determine whether the penalties applied in 2D depletion calculations for isotopic composition generation would be sufficient to cover atypical irradiation histories. In any case, if a FA with an extreme irradiation history is to be encountered in a criticality-safety evaluation of a transport cask or wet storage of used fuel, it is unlikely that all assemblies in the assessment will share such conditions.

In addition, some parameters were evaluated to characterize the conservatism of an ABP. This study demonstrates that the “R50” parameter of the FA (the ratio between the average burnup of the upper 50 cm of the FA and the total average burnup) is strongly correlated with its reactivity. A lower “R50” parameter indicates a more penalizing profile. However, this parameter fails to capture some irradiation effects occurring below the upper 50 cm part of the FA, which have a non-negligible impact on reactivity. Consequently, other parameters were examined, and the “R70” parameter (the ratio between the average burnup of the upper 70 cm of the FA and the total average burnup) seems to be a more relevant indicator to describe the conservatism of an ABP (or NABP).

This study is a step to help determining bounding NABPs for criticality-safety applications. This work will be extended with additional core configurations involving other types of fuel (e.g. MOX fuels) and different reactor controls conditions.

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